

Media coverage of January 2021 to December 2021, A content analysis of Political shows of selected private sector television programs

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Abstract

The study analyzed the political situations of Imran Khan's government through content analysis during the time period of January 2021 to December 2021. The study examines the anchor person's behavior towards the government participants through different indicators such as i.e., question tone, time given to the participants, the interruption made by anchor person towards the participants. Through random sampling 10 political talk shows were selected from each channel GEO news and ARY News. From GEO News Capital talk show was selected. From ARY News OFF The Record show was selected. The finding of the study was in term of time given Capital talk was given more time to the government participants and anchor person of the Capital talk was more neutral and less unfavorable towards the government participants. whereas the participants of the government were more interrupted. OFF The Record was given less time to the government participants and the anchor person asked mostly neutral questions and less unfavorable towards the government participants. The anchor person of OFF The Record were less interrupted the government persons.

Keywords: Political, Talk show, Anchor person, GEO news, ARY news.

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